

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

U.Vosikov

ERADICATING POVERTY IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES: A MULTIFACETED APPROACH

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

2023/MAY

